

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Mechanical properties tunability of three-dimensional polymeric structures in two-photon lithography

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Photoresist	Pillars					Drum-like structures	
	Laser powers (mW)					Writing speed ($\mu\text{m/s}$)	Laser power (mW)
IPL-780	8.8	10	13	16	100	13	60
IP-G 780	6	7	10	13	100	10	60
IP-Dip	5	6	7	10	13	100	60
Ormocomp®	8.5	13	15		100	13	60
SU8 2100	2.4	3.6	4.8		50	3.6	60

Figure S1: Parameters for fabrication of structures via 2PL.

Laser beam power (mW)	Pillar dimensions (l x w x h, μm)	
	12x12x120	24x24x240
7	1.6 \pm 0.2 GPa	1.3 \pm 0.1 GPa
10	2.6 \pm 0.1 GPa	2.8 \pm 0.1 GPa

Figure S2: Independence of the method from structure dimensions. As predicted by continuum mechanics beam theory, E does not change with the dimensions of the tested structure. Indeed, values for E of IP-Dip in the case of 12x12x120 μm and 24x24x240 μm are comparable, which accounts for the variations between them being caused only by experimental errors. Such an observation is meaningful and validates the applicability of continuum mechanics beam deflection theory to the presented characterization method.

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Figure S3: *E vs Displacement* graphs for IP-G 780 at 6mW (Panel A), 7mW (Panel B) and 13mW (Panel C).

Figure S4: E vs $Displacement$ graphs for Ormocomp® at 8.5mW (Panel A), 13mW (Panel B) and 15mW (Panel C).

Figure S5: E vs $Displacement$ graphs for SU8 2100 at 2.4mW (Panel A), 3.6mW (Panel B) and 4.8mW (Panel C).

Figure S6: *E vs Displacement* graphs for IP-Dip 780 at 7mW (Panel A), 10mW (Panel B) and 13mW (Panel C).

Figure S7: Fitting of stress relaxation curves. The force (F) vs time (t) data (black circles), describing stress relaxation for IP-G 780 at 7mW (Panel A) and SU8 2100 at 3.6mW (Panel B), were fitted with the following triexponential function (red curve):

$$F(t) = F_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t-t_0}{t_1}} + A_2 e^{-\frac{t-t_0}{t_2}} + A_3 e^{-\frac{t-t_0}{t_3}} .$$

For IP-G 780 $t_0=0.005s$, the 3 time constants $t_1=0.051s$, $t_2=0.809s$, $t_3=15.360s$, and the constant values $F_0=42.9\mu N$, $A_1=6.02\mu N$, $A_2=4.14\mu N$, $A_3=5.66\mu N$.

For SU8 2100 $t_0=0.005s$, the 3 time constants $t_1=0.049s$, $t_2=0.716s$, $t_3=8.423s$, and the constant values $F_0=84.1\mu N$, $A_1=2.60\mu N$, $A_2=2.71\mu N$, $A_3=3.13\mu N$

As a further verification of the effects of viscoelasticity in the force vs displacement measurements, the force decrease was evaluated in detail: the inset shows the first 200ms of the measurement, with the indication (red dotted line) of the maximum time needed for loading the structure in the specific measurement ($\Delta t_{load} \leq 6.5ms$).

Thereof, viscoelasticity effects are negligible in the force measurements reported in Fig. 2 obtained for $v_{load} = v_{unload} \approx 10^{-3}m/s$ and $\Delta t_{relaxation} = 0s$. Indeed, a total load-unload time span of $\Delta t_d = \Delta t_{load} + \Delta t_{relaxation} + \Delta t_{unload} = \Delta t_{load} + \Delta t_{unload} \leq 13ms$ (black dotted line) results in a decrease of $\approx 1.7\%$ with respect to the maximum value for IP-G 780, according to the fitting. For SU8 2100 decrease of registered force is $\approx 3.1\%$ with respect to the maximum, according to the fitting curve. In both cases, these values are within the error bars of the respective force vs displacement curves (IP-G 780 at 7mW and SU8 2100 at 3.6mW), accounting for stress relaxation to have no influence in the measurements obtained when $v_{load} \approx 10^{-3}m/s$, as already stated by the first time constant $t_1=51s > \Delta t_d$ for IP-G 780 and $t_1=49s > \Delta t_d$ for SU8 2100.

Figure S8: Laser Doppler vibrometer optical path scheme. The He-Ne 633nm laser wavelength shift during membrane vibration due to Doppler effect is measured by the interferometer, consisting of a reference beam and the target beam hitting the photodetector after having passed through a Bragg cell (heterodyne detection). A fixed, horizontal substrate is considered as plane reference. A camera within the vibrometer head allows the piezo substrate with the 2PL-written drum-like structure to be aligned under the laser beam. Output vertical displacement (on the order of 10^{-12}m) is displayed as a function of the piezo substrate vibration.

CAS number of resist components	MASS COMPOSITION ACCORDING TO MSDS	HYPOTHESIZED MASS COMPOSITION
3524-68-3	>95%	97%
77820-11-2	<5%	3%

CAS number 3524-68-3 	Molar mass	298.30 g/mol
	Total molar volume	240.24 cm ³ /mol
	Detail of structural unit molar volumes (cm ³ /mol)	
	-OH	8.04
	-C-	10.23
	>C<	3.33
	-O-	3.71
	>C=O	8.5
	-HC=	8.47
=CH ₂	11.94	
Component density = (molar mass)/(total molar volume) = 1.24 g/cm ³		

CAS number 77820-11-2 	Molar mass	327.40 g/mol
	Total molar volume	445.2 cm ³ /mol
	Detail of structural unit molar volumes (cm ³ /mol)	
	-CH ₃	13.67
	-C-	10.23
	>N-	4.33
	Thiophene	46.56
	Aromatic ring	96.64
	>C=O	8.5
	108.34	
Component density = (molar mass)/(total molar volume) = 0.74 g/cm ³		

$\text{IP-L 780 density} = (1.24 \cdot 0.97 + 0.74 \cdot 0.03) \text{ g/cm}^3 = 1.23 \text{ g/cm}^3$
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Figure S9: Calculation of standard molar volumes for IP-L 780 resist. Components of each resist were obtained from MSDS and a plausible mass composition was hypothesized proposed according to the declared ranges of values. Molar mass for each component was computed, and molar volumes of each structural unit of the component chemicals were obtained after values indicated in *van Krevelen and te Nijenhuis, Properties of Polymers, Elsevier, 2000*. For non-tabulated values, the most similar tabulated structural unit was considered. Density of the resist was then calculated as the ratios between molar mass and molar volume, weighted according to the resist mass composition